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EXPERIMENTAL AEROELASTIC ANALYSIS OF A 1.5-STAGE TRANSONIC COMPRESSOR WITH DIFFERENT STRUCTURAL MISTUNING PATTERNS

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ABSTRACT

Experimental investigations are carried out on the Transonic Compressor Darmstadt test rig focusing on convective non-synchronous vibrations and the potential to suppress them with structural mistuning. Various corrected rotor speeds, variable inlet guide vane stagger angles and three different structural mistuning configurations of the same rotor are analysed with the help of extensive time-resolving instrumentation. Characteristic parameters of the aeromechanic mechanism are determined and dependencies on the experimental variables are derived. It can be shown that the different eigenfrequency of the second blade type adds a degree of freedom to the coupling mechanism. The structural vibration amplitudes are evaluated as the safety-critical parameter showing both improvements and deteriorations resulting from the structural mistuning application. The potential of structural mistuning to prevent damages caused by convective non-synchronous vibration at specific speed lines is demonstrated. The mistuning application investigated in this work does not appear to be able to completely prevent the aeroelastic vibrations or to mitigate resulting amplitudes over the whole operating range of the compressor.

Keywords: Transonic Compressor, Compressor Aeroelasticity, Experimental Aeromechanics, Non-synchronous Vibrations, Structural Mistuning

NOMENCLATURE

1T	First torsional blade eigenmode
(a), (b), (c)	Mistuning configurations
BTT	Blade tip timing system
EO	Engine order
HCF	High cycle fatigue
IGV50	50% of max. inlet guide vane stagger angle
LE	Leading edge
M2	Blade eigenmode 2
N_{blades}	Number of blades
N45	45% of design speed
ND	Nodal diameter
NSV	Non-synchronous vibrations
SG	Strain gauge
T1, ... , T7	Time step marker
TE	Trailing edge
VIGV	Variable inlet guide vane
WPT	Wall pressure transducer
c	Circumferential propagation velocity
f	Frequency
\dot{m}	Mass flow
p	Pressure
u_{tip}	Blade tip velocity

α, β	Blade types
Δf	Frequency split
ε	Strain
ω	Angular velocity
<input type="checkbox"/> (a),(b),(c)	Configuration (a), (b), (c)
<input type="checkbox"/> A	Aerodynamic
<input type="checkbox"/> corr	Corrected
<input type="checkbox"/> eigen	Eigen-(frequency)
<input type="checkbox"/> in	Inlet
<input type="checkbox"/> rl	Red limit
<input type="checkbox"/> s	Static
<input type="checkbox"/> S	Structural
<input type="checkbox"/> sl	Stability limit
<input type="checkbox"/> t	Total
<input type="checkbox"/> rot	Rotating frame of reference
<input type="checkbox"/> stat	Stationary frame of reference

1 INTRODUCTION

In turbomachinery, mistuning describes the blade-to-blade non-uniformity of the rotor, i.e., a variation of the rotor characteristics around the circumference. Such variations can be either aerodynamic, in the form of varying flow conditions between the blade passages, or structural, most commonly regarding the eigenfrequencies of the blades. First investigations of mistuning, mainly considering unintentional structural mistuning resulting from manufacturing tolerances or wear, found that it has two major effects on blade vibration amplitudes: on the one hand, in the case of synchronous excitation (forced response), it can cause significantly higher amplitudes on individual blades in comparison to the tuned rotor (compare Whitehead [1], El-Bayoumi et al. [2]). On the other hand, it generally has a stabilising effect on NSVs such as flutter (compare Whitehead [3], Kaza et al. [4]). Since then, research has focused on mistuning with the aim of using its beneficial effect regarding NSV while limiting its unfavourable effect on forced response (e.g., Bendikson [5], Beirow et al. [6], Schöenborn et al. [7], Figaschewsky et al. [8], Vahdati et al. [9]).

Recent trends in compressor design, aiming for an increase in efficiency and a decrease in weight, result in a higher susceptibility of the front stage rotors to NSV. Firstly, this is due to increased overall pressure ratios and lower numbers of compressor stages, leading to increasing aerodynamic loads on the blades. Secondly, the application of blisk rotors and the reduction of blade thickness results in decreased structural damping of the rotor and stiffness of the blades. The rising susceptibility for NSV and its potential for structural damage due to high cycle fatigue (HCF) make suppressing measures such as aerodynamic and structural mistuning an important topic of research.

In this work, different structural mistuning applications are investigated experimentally on a 1.5-stage transonic compressor that is prone to the aeroelastic phenomenon called convective NSV. Similar fluid-structure-interactions were investigated as “self-excited rotating instabilities” by Holzinger et al. [10] and as “lock-in between part span rotating stall and blade vibration” by Zhao et al. [11]. The term “convective NSV” was first proposed by Stapelfeldt et al. [12] in 2020. The phenomenon was described by Brandstetter et al. [13] and Stapelfeldt et al. [12] based on the findings from experimental and numerical investigations. The mechanism is based on reinforcement of blade vibration and radial vortex shedding. High amplitudes of the first torsional eigenmode (1T) of the blades are characteristic, as this mode shows high deflections at the leading edge (LE), where excitation and vortex shedding take place. Convective NSV typically arises close to the aerodynamic stability limit because at these conditions, vortices are convected circumferentially from blade to blade and not out of the passage with the main flow. Lastly, the phenomenon is characterised by the formation of a coherent aerodynamic wave by the aerodynamic disturbances which travel around the rotor circumference. This aerodynamic wave and the structural wave of the rotor vibration which also travels around the circumference of the rotor lock in, which means that they modulate in frequency and phase.

Franke et al. [14] investigated the influence of different parameters on the coupling mechanism. It could be shown that the rotor speed does not affect the rotor-relative circumferential velocity of the aerodynamic disturbances in the stationary frame of reference $c^{\text{stat}}/u_{\text{tip}}$. However, an increase in rotor speed led to an increase of the aerodynamic nodal diameter ND_A , also called aerodynamic cell count or aerodynamic wave number. Increased pre-swirl, induced by variable inlet guide vanes (VIGVs), led to an increase in both $c^{\text{stat}}/u_{\text{tip}}$ and ND_A .

In the last years, various studies were conducted to investigate possible means to suppress convective NSV. Franke et al. [15] analysed the influence of the rotor blade count and the resulting change in blade pitch. With a rotor with reduced blade count, a reduction in blade vibration amplitudes could be achieved at design speed due to a shift of the impingement of the vortices further downstream of the leading edge. However, the lower blade number also caused higher amplitudes at part speed. Stapelfeldt et al. [16] and Franke et al. [17] demonstrated the potential of aerodynamic mistuning for the suppression of convective NSV experimentally and numerically. Structural mistuning was investigated numerically by Stapelfeldt et al. [16]. Its effectiveness was found to depend on both the frequency split, i.e., the difference in blade eigenfrequency, and the mistuning pattern, i.e., the distribution of mistuned blades around the rotor circumference. Experimental investigations on structural

mistuning were conducted by Brandstetter et al. [18] on a composite fan. In this case, the mistuned rotor configuration showed higher vibration amplitudes than the tuned one due the non-synchronous forced response nature of convective NSV.

The focus of the present study is on the experimental investigation of the potential of structural mistuning as a suppressing measure for convective NSV and its influence on the aeroelastic coupling mechanism.

2 METHODOLOGY

The experiments for this study have been carried out at the Transonic Compressor Darmstadt test rig, which is operated by the Institute of Gas Turbines and Aerospace Propulsion at Technical University of Darmstadt. As shown in Figure 1, ambient air is sucked in at the intake, passes through a settling chamber and is exhausted back to the ambient after passing through the compressor core. In this investigation, the compressor core is a 1.5-stage axial high pressure compressor consisting of VIGVs, a blisk rotor and a stator row. The rotor of this study was previously investigated in terms of aerodynamics by Radermacher et al. [19] and in terms of aeroelastics as a “rotor with reduced blade count” by Franke et al. [15].

The operating conditions of the stage, including rotor speed, mass flow and total pressure ratio, are controlled via the electric drive and the adjustable throttle at the outlet. Shaft speeds of up to 21,000 rpm can be reached, resulting in supersonic conditions at the rotor blade tip. Total pressure ratios of the investigated stages are typically around 1.5. The design mass flow of the test rig is 16 kg/s. The assessment of the operating point on the compressor map is performed with the help of total pressure, static pressure and total temperature measurements in the settling chamber, total pressure measurements at the stage inlet and outlet, as well as rotor speed measurements in the torque meter between the electrical drive and the rotor. In the event of rotating stall or high blade strains, an emergency bleed can be activated, which abruptly opens the throttle and takes the compressor stage back to a stable operating point by increasing the mass flow.

Three experimental variables are investigated in the course of the experiments, which are the corrected rotor speed, the VIGV stagger angle and the mistuning configuration. The four corrected rotor speeds included in this campaign are 45%, 80%, 95% and 100% of design speed of the rotor. For each rotor speed, up to four different VIGV stagger angles are investigated. In total, 13 combinations of rotor speed and VIGV angle are analysed. For each of these speed lines on the compressor map, three measurements are performed with different structural mistuning configurations. Configuration (a) is the baseline case without any intentional mistuning of the

blade eigenfrequencies, which have an unintentional mistuning of approximately $\pm 1\%$ to the mean value. Configuration (b) is the same rotor with a small number of blades with a lower eigenfrequency. Lastly, configuration (c) has additional blades with lower eigenfrequency. The blades with a higher eigenfrequency are referred to as type α blades, the other ones as type β blades. At all configurations, there are more blades of type α than of type β . The exact pattern and frequency split of the mistuning configurations is not shown due to proprietary reasons.

The measurement procedures are transient stall inception measurements along constant speed lines. This means that stable operating points with the corrected rotor speed and VIGV stagger angle of interest are set before the compressor is continuously throttled along the speed line towards the stability limit. The measurement is terminated by the rig operator, manually opening the emergency bleed when either the aerodynamic or the aeroelastic stability limit is reached. This means that either rotating stall sets in or structural vibration amplitudes caused by NSV exceed the HCF limits.

FIGURE 1: TRANSONIC COMPRESSOR DARMSTADT TEST RIG.

The aeroelastic analysis of the measurements is performed with the help of the time-resolving instrumentation shown in Figure 2. Firstly, eight strain gauges (SG) are applied on the pressure side of different blades, which are used for online monitoring of blade stresses during the measurements and for the analysis of blade vibration frequencies and amplitudes in the rotating frame of reference. They are sampled with a frequency of 100 kHz. Additionally, a capacitive blade tip timing system (BTT) is used for the evaluation of blade vibrations in the stationary frame of reference. In contrast to the strain gauges, the BTT system can assess the vibrations of all blades and can directly derive the structural nodal diameters of the vibration waves. Seven BTT sensors are distributed in the casing around the rotor circumference and in three axial planes. For the analysis of the unsteady aerodynamics, static wall pressure transducers

(WPT) are used, which have a sample rate of 500 kHz. The WPTs are arranged in an axial array covering the whole chord length of the rotor blade plus a short length upstream of it. Furthermore, single WPTs are distributed at nine different positions around the rotor circumference close to the leading edge axial position. With the help of the WPTs, aerodynamic fluctuations in the blade tip region can be investigated.

FIGURE 2: TIME-RESOLVING INSTRUMENTATION.

The combined analysis of the mentioned time-resolving measurement systems enables the identification of convective NSV and the determination of its characteristic parameters. These are the aerodynamic and structural nodal diameters and the relative propagation velocity of the aerodynamic disturbances around the rotor circumference. In case of convective NSV, distinct peaks can be found in the spectrograms of the strain gauges and WPTs at the leading edge. Figure 3 shows spectrograms for a config. (b) measurement. Time is expressed in revolutions with the stability limit being reached at revolution 0. Frequency is expressed in Engine Orders (EO). It can be seen that high amplitudes appear in the SG spectrogram at EO6.87, which is the frequency of the second eigenmode (M2) or first torsional eigenmode (1T). At the same time, a distinct peak appears in the WPT spectrogram at EO7.13. Following the derivations from Holzinger [20], the nodal diameter can be determined when the engine orders in the stationary and rotating frame of reference are known:

$$EO^{\text{stat}} = |EO^{\text{rot}} \pm ND| \quad (1)$$

Under the assumption of equal frequencies of aerodynamic and structural vibration in case of a lock-in, i.e. $EO_S^{\text{rot}} = EO_A^{\text{rot}}$, ND_A can be determined with Equation 1 to be $ND_A = 14$. As shown by Franke et al. [14], ND_S can be derived depending on the coupling mechanism case, i.e., the direction of rotation of the structural vibration wave:

$$N_{\text{blades}} = ND_A \pm ND_S \quad (2)$$

Additionally, ND_S is derived directly by the BTT system and can be used for the validation of the calculated parameters. Lastly, $c^{\text{stat}}/u_{\text{tip}}$ can be calculated when ND_A is known [20]:

$$\frac{c^{\text{stat}}}{u_{\text{tip}}} = \frac{EO_A^{\text{stat}}}{ND_A} = 1 - \frac{EO_A^{\text{rot}}}{ND_A} \quad (3)$$

The experimental data for $c^{\text{stat}}/u_{\text{tip}}$ is shown in Figure 3. The signals of the circumferentially distributed WPTs are cross-correlated in pairs and the time lag is derived for the maximum correlation value. The most probable propagation velocity is then determined with the time lag and the circumferential distance between the sensors for each sensor pair and time step. In Figure 3, the locked-in propagation velocity calculated with Equations 1 - 3 and the engine orders derived from the spectral analysis of the SGs and one WPT at the leading edge position, $c^{\text{stat}}/u_{\text{tip}} = 0.509$, is indicated as a dashed line. It can be seen that the propagation velocities determined with the spectral analysis and Equations 1 - 3 and with the cross-correlation of the circumferentially distributed WPTs show good agreement.

FIGURE 3: SPECTROGRAMS FROM SG (A) AND WPT (B) AND RELATIVE PROPAGATION VELOCITY (C) AT N80 IGV73, CONFIG. (B).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The methodology described in Section 2 is applied to all measurements in order to identify and characterise convective NSV. It is found that for all configurations, NSV occurs at all N45 and N80 speed lines, while none of the N95 and N100 speed lines show signs of an aeroelastic coupling. Therefore, the analysis is focused on the two lower rotor speeds. The characteristic parameters are determined using SG data from the rotating frame of reference, WPT and BTT data from the stationary frame of reference and Equations 1 - 3. The locked-in relative propagation velocity of the aerodynamic wave is shown in Figure 4 for all configurations, corrected rotor speeds and VIGV stagger angles. The stagger angles are indicated as a percentage of the maximum angle over all measurements and are defined positive in the direction of rotor rotation.

FIGURE 4: DOMINANT RELATIVE PROPAGATION VELOCITIES OVER VIGV STAGGER ANGLE FOR N45 AND N80 AND ALL CONFIGURATIONS.

The results show a clear trend of increased propagation velocity with increased VIGV stagger angle, especially at N45. This agrees with the expectation that increased pre-swirl caused by closed VIGVs increases the free propagation velocity around the circumference, which is also defined positive in the direction of rotor rotation (compare Brandstetter et al. [13], Franke et al. [14]). There appears to be no influence of the rotor speed on the relative propagation velocity. However, as the relative propagation velocity is related to the blade tip velocity u_{tip} , this means that the absolute propagation velocity c^{stat} increases with the rotor speed. The only operating point that does not follow the trend is N80 IGV73 at config. (c). This will be addressed later. The corresponding relation of the aerodynamic nodal diameter with corrected rotor speed, VIGV stagger angle and mistuning configuration can be seen in Figure 5. In this case, two trends are apparent: ND_A increases with increasing VIGV angles and

with decreasing rotor speeds. Equation 3 offers an explanation for these dependencies: when c^{stat}/u_{tip} increases with the VIGV angle, ND_A needs to increase to fulfil the equation as $EO_A^{rot} = EO_S^{rot}$ stays constant. When the rotor speed is increased, EO_S^{rot} decreases, because the increase in eigenfrequency due to centrifugal stiffening is negligible on the 1T mode of the investigated rotor. For constant c^{stat}/u_{tip} , ND_A then needs to decrease to enable aeromechanic coupling. Again, the config. (c) measurement at N80 IGV73 is the only one that does not follow the trend.

All described interdependencies agree with the findings from Franke et al. [14]. In both Figures 4 and 5, the mistuning configuration appears to influence the coupling mechanism, as both characteristic parameters change between configurations under the same operating conditions. However, there is no obvious trend. The small changes between the configurations could also be caused by differences in mechanical speed between the measurements. All measurements are performed with equal corrected rotor speeds. Varying ambient conditions between the measurement days lead to slightly different mechanical speeds which, in turn, influence the engine order in the rotating frame of reference. This effect needs to be investigated further. For more information, it is referred to Schneider [21].

FIGURE 5: DOMINANT AERODYNAMIC NODAL DIAMETERS OVER VIGV STAGGER ANGLE FOR N45 AND N80 AND ALL CONFIGURATIONS.

Besides the characteristic parameters of the aeromechanic coupling, the blade vibration amplitudes are assessed for all speed lines as they are the safety critical parameter. For this purpose, data from all strain gauges is analysed. They are divided into two groups which are applied on the surface of type α and type β blades. For type α , these are between six and eight SGs, depending on the configuration. Consequently, between zero and two SGs are applied on type β blades. A Fast Fourier

Transform is applied to the raw data and the amplitudes of the M2 (1T) frequency band are extracted. For each strain gauge, the maximum amplitude during the measurement is determined. This maximum amplitude is then related to the red limit strain ϵ_{rl} which was set beforehand. The yellow limit, which is at 50% of the red limit, was defined as the boundary for the aeroelastic stability limit and, thereby, for the termination of the measurement procedure. Figure 6 shows the resulting relative strains for all measurements and for both blade types. Each bar represents the minimum and maximum amplitude of all strain gauges on the corresponding blade type. In case of only one SG on the blade type or for very small differences, a bar with a height of 4% is chosen for better visualisation.

FIGURE 6: MAXIMUM STRUCTURAL VIBRATION AMPLITUDES OF BLADE TYPES α AND β FOR ALL N45 AND N80 MEASUREMENTS.

On the type α blades, very large differences between minimum and maximum amplitudes of the different strain gauges can be seen. Especially during the measurements with the highest maximum amplitudes like N80 IGV0 and IGV50, ratios of 3 to 4 between the minimum and the maximum strain occur. On the one hand, these can be a direct consequence of the aeromechanic coupling mechanism which excites some blades more than others, e.g., due to the unintentional mistuning of the type α blades. On the other hand, uncertainties due to the strain gauge positioning and sensitivity, as well as the calculation of the relative strain with the assigned limits are

not negligible. The limits of each SG position type result from the strain ratios derived from numerical simulations. One type is optimised for the 1T eigenmode, while another type is optimised for higher eigenmodes and has a significantly lower sensitivity for the 1T mode. Furthermore, the reaction time between reaching the stability limit and manually opening the emergency bleed by the rig operator plays an important role for the maximum amplitudes that are reached during the measurements, especially in case of amplitudes with high growth rates. One example is the N80 IGV0 measurement of config. (a) which shows much lower amplitudes than the config. (b) and (c) measurements. This is a consequence of an unintentional early termination of the measurement by the rig operator. Because of the aforementioned reasons, the results shown in Figure 6 cannot be used for quantitative comparisons between different measurements. However, some trends and fundamental differences between the measurements can be identified.

Generally, the vibration amplitudes are lower at the lower rotor speed. For blade type α at both N45 and N80, the amplitudes increase with decreased VIGV angle. This could be a result of higher mass flows and, consequently, higher dynamic pressures in the flow which, in turn, lead to a higher level of transient aerodynamic forcing on the blades. Furthermore, higher incidences at the rotor leading edge due to less pre-swirl can cause stronger vortex shedding due to local flow separation and impingement of the vortices closer to the leading edge of the following blades. The same trend can be seen at blade type β for N45. However, for N80, an opposing trend is apparent: amplitudes increase with increasing VIGV angles.

For the assessment of the structural mistuning as a suppressing measure, the amplitudes shown in Figure 6 are compared to the limit strains. Measurements with maximum amplitudes above the yellow limit reach the aeroelastic before the aerodynamic stability limit, which means that there is a potential loss of stability margin. Measurements with maximum amplitudes below the yellow limit are terminated at the onset of rotating stall. There is no loss in stability margin due to aeroelastic vibrations at these speed lines. The goal of the structural mistuning is to reduce maximum amplitudes sufficiently to enable reaching the aerodynamic stability limit. This is the case at two speed lines, which are N45 IGV0 and, especially, N80 IGV73, which is the nominal VIGV setting at N80. At N80 IGV100, the opposite is the case: amplitudes stayed below the yellow limit for config. (a) and (b), but the type β blades exceed the limit for config. (c). These speed lines are analysed in detail in the following sections.

3.1 Analysis of N80 Speed Lines

The structural vibration amplitudes on blade types α and β , as well as the aerodynamic fluctuation amplitudes measured by a WPT at the leading edge, are shown in Figure 7 for N80 IGV73. The aerodynamic amplitudes are extracted for the

corresponding coupling frequencies. On the x-axis, the corrected mass flow is indicated, which is reduced continuously during the measurement. It is normalised with the minimum mass flow achieved at the config. (b) measurement. The maximum amplitude of all the considered SGs is displayed at all time steps. In the detailed analysis, the SG amplitudes for blade type α only include the four SGs which are optimised for the 1T eigenmode.

FIGURE 7: STRUCTURAL AND AERODYNAMIC AMPLITUDES OVER CORRECTED MASS FLOW AT N80 IGV73 FOR CONFIG. (B) AND (C).

At config. (b), type α SG amplitudes show a sudden rise with a simultaneous increase in aerodynamic amplitude. They increase from a level of background noise to exceeding the yellow limit during a decrease in mass flow of less than 1%, which corresponds to under 4 seconds of measurement time. Type β amplitudes begin to increase only when type α amplitudes are already reaching the limit and stay at more than five times lower values. At config. (c), the coupling mechanism changes fundamentally. Amplitudes of both blade types begin to increase at approximately the same mass flow as the config. (b) measurement. However, they increase with a much lower growth rate and stagnate without reaching the aeroelastic stability limit. Because of this, the aerodynamic stability limit is reached and an increase in stability margin of nearly 3% relative to config. (b) is achieved. Interestingly, blade type β shows higher amplitudes than type α and the difference between the two types is significantly smaller in comparison to the config. (b) measurement.

The relation between the amplitudes of the two blade types becomes more apparent in Figure 8. Here, they are shown over the frequency measured with the SGs in the rotating frame of reference and normalised with the frequency split of the applied mistuning Δf and the eigenfrequency of the type α blades $f_{eigen,\alpha}^{rot}$. The time steps which are depicted in Figure 8 are marked as T1 and T2 in Figure 7. They are chosen to be the time steps with the highest amplitudes. Similar to Figure 7, the maximum amplitudes of all considered SGs are shown. As the aerodynamic amplitudes are measured in the stationary frame of reference by the WPT, they are transformed into the rotating frame of reference with Equation 1 and normalised accordingly.

FIGURE 8: STRUCTURAL AND AERODYNAMIC AMPLITUDES OVER FREQUENCY AT N80 IGV73 FOR CONFIG. (B) AND (C).

The maximum amplitude of both blade types, as well as the aerodynamic fluctuations, are located at the same frequency at the config. (b) measurement. As the amplitude of blade type α is much higher, this indicates that the aeromechanic coupling is occurring at the type α eigenfrequency. The type β blades show significantly lower amplitudes because they are not excited exactly at their eigenfrequency. At config. (c), the eigenfrequencies of both blade types are visible. It can be seen that the highest amplitude and the peak of the WPT amplitudes are located at the lower eigenfrequency of blade type β . This means that due to the additional blades of type β compared to config. (b), the coupling shifted from one blade type to the other. After this shift, blade type β shows only one peak at its own eigenfrequency, while type α has two peaks with a

higher amplitude at the own eigenfrequency. Therefore, the result is a distribution of the vibration energy over the two eigenfrequencies and lower overall maximum amplitudes.

For the N80 IGV100 speed line, which shows a magnification in vibration amplitudes, the corresponding analysis is carried out. Firstly, the amplitudes from SGs and WPT over corrected mass flow can be seen in Figure 9. Once again, the mass flow is normalised with the mass flow at the stability limit of config. (b). In this case, this is the mass flow at which rotating stall sets in. The vibration amplitudes of both blade types stay relatively low and only slightly increase just before the aerodynamic stability limit. The difference between the blade types is small, with the type α amplitudes being marginally higher. Similar to the N80 IGV73 speed line, the coupling mechanism changes between configurations. At config. (c), the type α blades show a similar progression with almost equal amplitudes over the mass flow as in the config. (b) measurement. However, type β displays significantly increased amplitudes that exceed the yellow limit strain. This means that the aeroelastic stability limit is reached first at this configuration. In this case, this does not result in a significant loss in stability margin, as the aeroelastic limit is reached at approximately the same corrected mass flow as the aerodynamic stability limit.

FIGURE 9: STRUCTURAL AND AERODYNAMIC AMPLITUDES OVER CORRECTED MASS FLOW AT N80 IGV100 FOR CONFIG. (B) AND (C).

The structural and aerodynamic amplitudes over frequency are shown in Figure 10 for this speed line. It is apparent

that, once again, a shift of the coupling mechanism from the eigenfrequency of blade type α to type β occurs between the configurations. In this case, the vibrational energy is distributed over the two frequencies at the configuration with less type β blades. Because of this, the maximum amplitudes of both types stay below the limit and the aerodynamic stability limit can be reached. Due to the shift to type β at config. (c), the vibrational energy gets concentrated at the lower eigenfrequency resulting in a significantly increased maximum amplitude.

FIGURE 10: STRUCTURAL AND AERODYNAMIC AMPLITUDES OVER FREQUENCY AT N80 IGV100 FOR CONFIG. (B) AND (C).

The following conclusions can be derived from the analysis of the two N80 speed lines:

- The addition of type β blades between config. (b) and (c) with a total number that is still lower than that of type α leads to a shift of the coupling mechanism from the type α eigenfrequency to the lower type β eigenfrequency at high VIGV speed lines.
- At the IGV73 speed line, which is the nominal VIGV setting for this rotor at N80, this shift results in a significant reduction in the maximum structural vibration amplitude and thus in a gain in stability margin of approximately 3%.
- At the IGV100 speed line, maximum amplitudes increase significantly after the shift without leading to a noticeable loss in stability margin.
- With the second blade type, i.e., the introduction of type β blades, the aeroelastic coupling mechanism gains an additional degree of freedom. As discussed before, in case

of only one blade type, ND_A and $c^{\text{stat}}/u_{\text{tip}}$ need to adapt to fulfil Equation 3. As a consequence, increasing VIGV stagger angles generally cause both parameters to increase. With a second blade type, EO_A^{rot} can also adapt by changing between the two blade type eigenfrequencies. With this additional degree of freedom, the general relationship between the VIGV angle and the aerodynamic nodal diameter is no longer valid. The aeroelastic coupling has two options when the VIGV angle is increased: either the aerodynamic nodal diameter is increased, or the engine order in the rotating frame of reference, i.e. the coupling frequency, is reduced. The latter corresponds to a shift of the coupling mechanism from blade type α to type β towards a lower eigenfrequency.

- Two aforementioned observations can be explained with this interdependency: firstly, the decrease in ND_A from IGV50 to IGV73 at config. (c) as shown in Figure 5 is enabled by the additional degree of freedom. The second observation is the increase in structural vibration amplitudes on blade type β towards increasing VIGV stagger angles at N80, as shown in Figure 6. This is a consequence from the tendency to reduce the engine order in the rotating frame of reference and, thereby, shift the coupling mechanism to the type β blades towards higher VIGV stagger angles.

3.2 Analysis of N45 IGV0 Speed Line

The third measurement to be analysed in more detail is the N45 IGV0 speed line of config. (c). It is of interest not because of strongly changing maximum amplitudes but because of an increase in type β amplitudes and, especially, because of an interesting behaviour during continuous throttling which is described in the following. The SG and WPT amplitudes over corrected mass flow and frequency of this measurement are shown in Figure 11 corresponding to the representations in Figures 7 - 10. In this case, the corrected mass flow is normalised with the aerodynamic stability limit mass flow of this speed line and configuration. The measurement can be divided into three phases which are indicated in Figures 11 and 12. In phase (I), structural vibration amplitudes rise with a moderate growth rate, with the amplitudes of type α blades being between 1.5 and 2 times higher than those of type β blades. At a normalised mass flow of approximately 1.05, before reaching the yellow limit, both structural and aerodynamic amplitudes drop before beginning to increase again. In phase (II), the amplitudes of type β are more than 2 times higher than of type α . At a similar level as the first drop, amplitudes fall a second time between mass flows of 1.02 and 1.01. In phase (III), the amplitudes of both blade types begin to increase slightly again on a similar level before the aerodynamic stability limit is reached and the measurement is terminated.

The point of highest amplitudes of each phase is marked with

(T5), (T6) and (T7) in Figure 11. These time steps are included and marked accordingly in the lower half showing the amplitudes over the frequency. The three phases can be recognised and separated clearly by their coupling frequencies. In phase (I), the coupling takes place at the blade type α eigenfrequency. At the transition to phase (II), the coupling shifts from type α to type β while the structural and aerodynamic nodal diameters stay equal. At the start of phase (III), the coupling shifts back to the type α blades and changes its nodal diameters by 1. The significantly lower SG amplitudes with almost equal WPT amplitudes indicate that in this phase, the blades are excited at a frequency which is different to the type α eigenfrequency.

FIGURE 11: STRUCTURAL AND AERODYNAMIC AMPLITUDES OVER CORRECTED MASS FLOW AND FREQUENCY AT N45 IGV0, CONFIG. (C).

Figure 12 offers an additional perspective on the changes in the aeromechanic coupling. In analogy to Figure 3, the spectrograms from SGs and WPT, as well as the relative propagation velocity are shown over time, expressed in revolutions before the stability limit. The mean of all strain gauge spectrograms is shown in this figure instead of only the spectrogram of one single SG in order to achieve a better visualisation of all of the three coupling frequencies. In this representation, the frequencies of SGs and WPT are normalised with the frequency split and the corresponding dominant frequency during phase (I), $f_{S,I}^{\text{rot}}$ and $f_{A,I}^{\text{stat}}$. The relative propagation velocity is normalised with the locked-in propagation velocity calculated with Equation 3 for the first coupling phase.

In the SG spectrogram, the changes of the coupling mechanism can be seen at approximately revolutions -500 and -200 in line with Figure 11. In the WPT spectrogram, both changes are reflected in an increase in frequency, as it is measured in the stationary frame of reference. Lastly, the changes in relative propagation velocity are shown. The locked-in velocities calculated with Equation 3 for each phase are indicated with dashed lines. Especially at the second transition, the measured values follow the increase that is theoretically calculated. This means that increased back pressure and reduced mass flow lead to an increase in relative propagation velocity during this measurement. This, in turn, results in changes in the coupling mechanism that can be explained with Equation 3: in the first transition, the aerodynamic nodal diameter does not change, while the engine order in the rotating frame of reference reduces. This is reflected in a shift of the aeromechanic coupling from the type α blades to the type β blades. In the second transition, $EO_A^{rot} = EO_S^{rot}$ increases again to the eigenfrequency of the type α blades while ND_A increases. Therefore, in this case, the continuous throttling has a similar influence on the aeromechanic phenomenon as the previously discussed increase in VIGV stagger angle.

FIGURE 12: SPECTROGRAMS FROM SG (A) AND WPT (B) AND RELATIVE PROPAGATION VELOCITY (C) AT N45 IGVO, CONFIG. (C).

The following conclusions can be derived from the analysis of the N45 IGVO measurement with config. (c):

- The rising back pressure during throttling results in increasing propagation velocities which influence the other characteristic parameters of the aeroelastic coupling.
- Similar to the N80 measurements, the increase in relative propagation velocity leads to either a change of the nodal diameters or a shift of the coupling mechanism from one blade type to the other. The latter is only possible for a rotor with structural mistuning.
- Depending on the frequency split, either the blade type shift or the change in nodal diameter takes place first. For small frequency splits, the blade type shift happens first because the ratio between the two eigenfrequencies is smaller than the ratio between two neighbouring nodal diameters.
- Changes in nodal diameter and blade type can help prevent reaching the aeroelastic limit as amplitudes drop and begin to rise again when they occur. However, this highly depends on the growth rates of the amplitudes and the mass flows at which such changes occur.

4 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The aeroelastic vibration phenomenon called convective NSV and the possibility to suppress it with structural mistuning of the rotor were investigated experimentally. In order to do that, measurements with different corrected rotor speeds, VIGV stagger angles and with three rotor configurations were carried out at the Transonic Compressor Darmstadt test rig. The rotor configurations included one without intentional mistuning and two mistuned rotors with different ratios of numbers of type α to type β blades. With the help of three different time-resolving measurement systems, the fluid-structure-interaction could be analysed in detail. These comprise a blade tip timing system and static wall pressure transducers in the rotor casing, as well as strain gauges on the blade surfaces.

The characteristic parameters of the aeromechanic coupling were determined for all measurements showing convective NSV. These are the aerodynamic and structural nodal diameters and the relative propagation velocity of the aerodynamic disturbances. Two previously observed relations could be confirmed: an increase in rotor speed leads to a decrease in the aerodynamic nodal diameter and an increase in VIGV stagger angle results in an increase in both relative propagation velocity and aerodynamic nodal diameter. However, the configuration with the highest ratio of type β blades did not follow these trends at all speed lines.

The structural vibration amplitudes were analysed for all measurements and compared to the HCF limits. Generally, higher rotor speeds and lower VIGV stagger angles resulted

in higher amplitudes on the blades. Only on blade type β at 80% design speed, an increase in VIGV angle led to higher amplitudes. The most significant changes regarding the stability limits occurred at two N80 speed lines: at one VIGV setting, the amplitudes decreased from config. (b) to config. (c) and the aerodynamic stability limit could be reached. At another one, amplitudes increased from one configuration to the next exceeding the yellow limit strain and, thereby, reaching the aeroelastic stability limit.

The analysis of the two speed lines with changes regarding the stability limit showed that, in both cases, the aeromechanic coupling shifted from one blade type to the other between the configurations. In one case, this resulted in a gain in stability margin of approximately 3%. In the other case, no stability margin was lost because the aeroelastic stability limit is reached at approximately the same mass flow as the aerodynamic limit. It was shown that with the structural mistuning, the aeroelastic mechanism gains an additional degree of freedom. Apart from a change in nodal diameter, it can react to changing VIGV angles with a shift in the coupling frequency from one blade type to the other.

At N45 IGV0, changes in both the nodal diameters and the blade type occurred during the continuous throttling of the config. (c) measurement. The increased back pressure and reduced mass flow resulted in rising relative propagation velocities which, in turn, led to a shift from one blade type to the other and, after that, to a change in nodal diameter. This demonstrated again the two possibilities that a mistuned system has to react to changing relative propagation velocities. In this case, the aerodynamic stability limit could be reached because the amplitudes dropped before exceeding the HCF limits at both mechanism changes.

The structural vibration amplitudes on the rotor blades could be reduced and kept under the HCF limit at the N80 IGV73 speed line with the structural mistuning application of config. (c). For this compressor stage, this is the speed line with the nominal VIGV stagger angle setting for the corresponding corrected speed. Therefore, the mistuning application can be evaluated as successful in terms of convective NSV suppression at a relevant operating condition. However, this mistuning configuration is not suitable for the prevention of convective NSV over the whole operating range of the compressor stage.

It can be concluded that structural mistuning is a suitable measure for the enlargement of the operating range of a compressor stage in specific regions on the compressor map. In case of application of structural mistuning, the consequences for other parts of the operating range need to be assessed considering all blade types.

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